

Shortened Call for Proposal for the PREMIERE Multi-actor Roleplay workshop

HORIZON-CL6-2024-BIODIV-02-3-two-stage: Promoting minor crops in farming systems¹

<i>Indicative budget</i>	The total indicative budget for the topic is EUR 10.00 million.
<i>Type of Action</i>	Research and Innovation Action
<i>Eligibility conditions</i>	The proposal must apply the multi-actor approach.

Successful proposals will contribute to the following outcomes:

- Increased evidence of the environmental benefits of minor crops;
- Farmers make use of a wider range of crops, and combination of crops;
- Minor crops are integrated in farming systems promoting their environmental benefits;
- Increased resilience and climate adaptation of farming systems vis-a-vis biotic/abiotic stress;
- Feed and food industry make use of minor crops;
- Creation of new avenues for farmers and value chains through a wider range of products.

Scope:

Farmers face increasing pressure to shift production towards lower input systems, while continuing to ensure sufficient supplies of food and non-food products. Activities shall release the value of minor crops and promote their broader use in breeding, farming and in food/non-food value chains. For the purpose of this topic, minor crops are defined as underutilised crops.

- Promote the access to minor crops engaging in breeding activities
- Improve agronomic management practices for minor crops

Explore the effects and benefits of minor crops and demonstrate the ecosystems services supported by farming system diversification and the integration of minor crops (if applicable, including novel crop rotations).

- Identify and test avenues for marketing and processing of more diverse farming outputs across the value chain;
- Promote the uptake of minor crops through the development of guidelines and wide-spread practical demonstrations taking into account a range of farming systems, pedo-climatic conditions and value chains;
- Support capacity building, training and education enabling farmers/growers to adopt sustainable agricultural practices.

Activities must implement the **multi-actor approach**, thus ensure an adequate involvement of researchers, farmers, advisors, food industry, and other players in the value chain and consumers. Communication and outreach to a wide range of stakeholders is essential.

¹ Minor Crops: Diverse Nutzpflanzen (zB Kräuter, Gemüse, Beerenobst), die einen vergleichsweise hohen Marktwert haben, in begrenzten Gebieten angebaut werden und für die vergleichsweise wenig Pflanzenschutzmittel zugelassen sind.